

Plain English Summary (short form)

Why did we do this study?

Paediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) and Paediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) are conditions whereby young people suddenly experience several physical and psychiatric symptoms. PANS and PANDAS may persist for years, usually getting much worse at certain points during the year. The symptoms of PANS/PANDAS can be extremely severe and have a huge impact on families.

There is a lack of consensus in the research about all aspects of the conditions. This uncertainty means that patients, families and suspected patients experience additional challenges beyond those presented by having the conditions. It also makes it difficult to direct future research, risking wasted effort and slow progress.

To gain a clear picture of the evidence and help address these issues, we conducted an 'Evidence and gap map' (EGM). This is an interactive way of presenting evidence, so that anyone using the EGM could find out how much research has been done on any aspect of the conditions, and see gaps in the evidence.

What did we do?

We aimed to find every study about PANS/PANDAS that collected some data. To do this, we searched comprehensively and included any type of scientific research. We sorted through over 9000 papers, and after screening out all the irrelevant studies, we were left with 445 items about PANS/PANDAS.

We coded these 445 so that, once they were in the EGM, they could be found by their key characteristics. For example, map users could see how many studies were about diagnosis, or from a certain country, or look into specific symptoms like sleep difficulties or aggression. We coded dozens of features, and worked closely with expert professionals, parents of young people with the conditions, and young people with PANS/PANDAS to make the EGM relevant and useful.

What were the main findings?

About half of the studies came from the USA, and there was little from the UK. Much of the research was from studies that describe one or two patients, which is not useful for patients or healthcare providers. Despite having a lot of recent evidence, there are large gaps in the understanding of PANS/PANDAS.

In summary

Overall, most studies about PANS/PANDAS are of low value when seeking to understand the conditions, or advance knowledge about diagnosis or treatment. The EGM provides a valuable resource that will allow patients, carers and clinicians to access research, and help plan for future studies.